

A new combination in *Machilus* (Lauraceae)

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Abstract: *Persea endothrix* Kosterm. is transferred to *Machilus* Rumph. ex Nees as *Machilus endothrix* (Kosterm.) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar.

Keywords: Borneo, Holotype, Malaysia, *Persea endothrix*, Sabah

Introduction

Kostermans (1974) described *Persea endothrix* based on material collected by G. Mikil from Kinabalu, Tenompok Forest Reserve, Ranau, Sabah, Malaysia. However, *Persea* Mill. is now considered to be restricted to the New World, and the diagnostic characters provided in the protologue of *P. endothrix* including vegetative and floral features correspond to those of *Machilus* Rumph. ex Nees. The species is therefore transferred here to *Machilus*.

Taxonomic treatment

Machilus endothrix (Kosterm.) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Persea endothrix* Kosterm., Reinwardtia 9(1): 111. 1974

Holotype: Malaysia, Borneo, Sabah, Ranau, Tenompok Forest Reserve, Kinabalu, 4000 ft., 15 March 1966, G. Mikil 56521 (L0036935!, Figure 1).

Distribution: Malaysia (Sabah).

Figure 1: Holotype of *Persea endotherix* Kosterm. (L0036935, © Naturalis Biodiversity Center, Leiden)

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Reference

Kostermans, A.J.G.H. (1974). Materials for a revision of Lauraceae IV. *Reinwardtia* 9(1): 97–115.